

HamSCI Poster Template Preview

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Abstract

Put abstract here.

Introduction

- Provides a brief background
- Gets the viewers interested
- Places work in context of literature
- Cite when necessary
- Use figures
- Give them captions

Method/Experiment

- How did you do it?
- What did you use?
- Use images

Data and Analysis

- This is the largest section
- Put all plots in here
- Begin to conclude
- Brief summary of results

Conclusion

- Discusses major results
- Relate to the theory
- Discuss new questions/future work

References

Put any references here.

Acknowledgements

Put acknowledgements here.